

SPECIES COMPOSITION OF TYDEOID MITES IN ARMENIA

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The paper presents the results of studies on tydeoid mites in Armenia, conducted for the period 2020–2022, which are based on the data of our own collections. The message is a continuation of our research on the Armenian tydeoid fauna. For the first time, four new species of ticks were noted for the fauna of Armenia. The types of identified species are stored in the collections of the Laboratory of Experimental Zoology of the Institute of Zoology of the Scientific Center of Zoology and Hydroecology of the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Armenia.

Keywords: Tydeoid mites, tydeoids, mites, species, fauna

ВИДОВОЙ СОСТАВ ТИДЕОИДНЫХ КЛЕЩЕЙ В АРМЕНИИ

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Աշխատության մեջ ներկայացված են 2020-2022 թթ. ընթացքում Հայաստանի տիդեոիդ-տզերի հետազոտության արդյունքները, որոնց հիմքում դրված են սեփական հավաքագրումների տվյալները: Աշխատանքը Հայաստանի տիդեոիդ-տզերի ֆաունայի վերաբերյալ մեր հետազոտության շարունակությունն է: Առաջին անգամ Հայաստանի ֆաունայի համար նշվում են տզերի 30 նոր տեսակներ: Հայտնաբերված տեսակները մանրապատրաստուկների տեսքով պահվում են Հայաստանի Հանրապետության Կենդանաբանության և հիդրոէկոլոգիայի գիտական կենտրոնի կենդանաբանության ինստիտուտի անողնաշարների հավաքածուներում:

Բանալի բառեր - տիդեոիդ տզեր, տիդեոիդներ, տզեր, տեսակներ, ֆաունա:

В работе представлены результаты исследований по клещам-тидеидам Армении, проведенных за период 2020–2022 гг., в основу которых положены данные собственных сборов. Сообщение является продолжением наших исследований по фауне тидеид Армении. Впервые для фауны Армении отмечены 30 новых вида клещей. Типы выявленных видов хранятся в коллекциях лаборатории экспериментальной зоологии Института зоологии Научного центра зоологии и гидроэкологии Национальной академии наук Республики Армения.

Ключевые слова: клещи-тидеиды, тидеиды, клещи, виды, фауна

Introduction

In recent years, acarologists have shown increasing interest in tydeoid mites (Tydeoidea), which have important both theoretical and practical significance. Tydeoids (Tydeoidea, Kramer, 1877) belong to the order Acariformes and are found almost everywhere. The family Tydeoidea (Trombidiformes: Prostigmata) represents a large and taxonomically complex group with a worldwide distribution (Krantz, 1978). Some species have a broad distribution, while at the same time they are associated with specific habitats (Kaźmierski, 1998).

Representatives of this group occur from Antarctica to tropical regions, from seashores to alpine meadows, as well as from the coldest areas to dry and hot deserts (André and Fain, 2000).

Tydeoid mites play an important role in reducing the impact of plant pathogens by effectively cleaning leaf surfaces. Many herbivorous tydeoid species are involved in regulating the abundance of phytophagous organisms. At the same time, tydeoids serve as a food source for beneficial predatory species in agrocenoses (Kaźmierski, 1998).

Thus, it is evident that mites have important theoretical and applied significance. Considering the above, it should be emphasized that the relevance of studying this group is determined both by

their importance as a group of arthropods and by the fact that they remain insufficiently studied in our country.

Material and methods

The study material includes tydeoid mites collected and recorded from different regions of the Republic of Armenia, which are stored in the invertebrate collections of the Scientific Center of Zoology and Hydroecology of the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Armenia.

The study was based on field collections conducted in various regions of Armenia as well as on relevant literature sources. Within the framework of this research, the collected material originates from different biomes of the country. The material used for this work consists of tydeoid mites collected from sites located in various physico-geographical zones of Armenia. It should be noted that the tydeoid species presented in this study, as already mentioned, are recorded for the first time in the fauna of Armenia.

Sampling was carried out from late spring to late autumn. More than 200 scientific expeditions were conducted across nearly all regions of Armenia, resulting in the recording of 31 tydeoid mite species new to the fauna of the Republic of Armenia. In total, 195 specimens were collected.

For fieldwork, polyethylene bags, needles, soft brushes, and containers were used. Plant leaves, bark, and twig samples were collected and placed in plastic bags for subsequent stereomicroscopic examination. To determine species identity and morphological characteristics, microscope slides were prepared to enable more precise investigation.

The slides were prepared as follows: collected mites were placed on a glass slide with a drop of Faure–Berlese medium, their appendages were arranged, and the coverslip was carefully applied to avoid air bubbles. To remove any remaining air bubbles, the preparations were gently heated over a flame. Afterward, the slides were kept in a horizontal position for 5–10 days at 50–60°C in a thermostat or drying chamber, during which the specimens were cleared and fully processed. Subsequently, the edges of the coverslips were sealed with varnish. Each prepared slide was labeled with information on the collection site, including GPS coordinates, date (day, month, year), and collector's name (Rek, 1959).

Species identification was carried out using an MBS-10 stereomicroscope. After preliminary processing, the mites were fixed in Faure–Berlese solution. For accurate taxonomic identification, a comprehensive literature database was compiled, including relevant scientific articles, original species descriptions, taxonomic keys, nomenclatural works, and morphological descriptions.

Research Results

The study resulted in the identification and scientific description of 31 species of tydeoid mites, all of which are reported from Armenia for the first time.

The Species Composition of Tydeoid Mites (Acariformes: Tydeoidea) of Armenia

1	<i>Brachytydeus catenulate</i> (Thor, 1931)
2	<i>Brachytydeus caudatus</i> (Dugès, 1834)
3	<i>Brachytydeus dumosus</i> (Kuznetsov, 1973)
4	<i>Brachytydeus echinulata</i> (Kuznetsov, 1971)
5	<i>Brachytydeus elegans</i> (Baker, 1965)
6	<i>Brachytydeus granulosa</i> (Canestrini, 1886)
7	<i>Brachytydeus insignia</i> (Kuznetsov, 1971)
8	<i>Brachytydeus mali</i> (Oudemans, 1929)
9	<i>Brachytydeus minuta</i> (Kuznetsov, 1971)
10	<i>Brachytydeus obnoxia</i> (Kuznetsov & Zapletina, 1972)
11	<i>Brachytydeus ocelata</i> (Kuznetsov, 1973)
12	<i>Brachytydeus placita</i> (Livshitz, 1973)
13	<i>Brachytydeus reticulate</i> (Oudemans, 1928)
14	<i>Brachytydeus viennensis</i> (Inat, 1993)
15	<i>Brachytydeus visenda</i> (Kuznetsov, in Kuznetsov & Livshitz 1973)

16	<i>Calotydeus cumbrensis</i> (Baker, 1944)
17	<i>Calotydeus tauricus</i> (Kuznetsov, 1971)
18	<i>Metalorryia delicata</i> (Kuznetsov, 1971)
19	<i>Paralorryia formosa</i> (Kuznetsov, 1971)
20	<i>Tydeus electus</i> (Kuznetsov, 1971)
21	<i>Tydeus inclutus</i> (Livshitz, 1973)
22	<i>Tydeus kochi</i> (Oudemans, 1928)
23	<i>Tydeus momeni</i> (Khanjani & Ueckermann, 2003)
24	<i>Tydeus praeditus</i> (Livshitz & Zapletina, 1973)
25	<i>Tydeus californicus</i> (Banks, 1904)
26	<i>Pronematus anconai</i> (Baker, 1944)
27	<i>Pronematus bonatii</i> (Canestrini, 1886)
28	<i>Pronematus rapidus</i> (Kuznetsov, 1972)
29	<i>Pronematus vandykei</i> (Baker 1968)
30	<i>Proctotydaeus (Proctotydulus) oblongus</i> (Kuznetsov, 1973)
31	<i>Paratriophtydeus protydeus</i> (Baker, 1943)

Conclusion

The first comprehensive study of tydeoid mites (Acariformes: Tydeoidea) conducted in Armenia represents a significant contribution to the development of acarological research in the country. The results demonstrate that Armenia's diverse landscapes and climatic conditions provide favorable habitats for a rich and diverse tydeoid mite fauna.

Field and laboratory investigations carried out across different regions of the republic revealed that tydeoid mites are widely distributed on fruit plants and are represented by considerable species diversity. During the course of this study, 31 new species of tydeoid mites were discovered and scientifically described, significantly enriching knowledge of both the Armenian and global acarofauna.

The findings highlight that, despite its relatively small territory, Armenia encompasses a wide range of geographical and ecological conditions that support a high diversity of microarthropods. The data obtained provide a valuable foundation for future taxonomic, ecological, and biological studies and may have practical applications in biodiversity conservation, ecosystem monitoring, and plant protection.

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